

Received: January 04, 2026 | Revised: January 15, 2026 | Accepted: January 19, 2026 | Published: January 25, 2026

Leveraging Artificial Intelligence for Sustainable Development Goals: A Multidisciplinary Perspective

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Abstract

This study explored motivation for learning and its relationship to undergraduate majors in engineering and social work. Three motivation measurement scales--the Basic Psychological Needs Scale (BPNS), the Achievement Goal Orientation Scale (AGOS), and the Situational Motivation Scale (SIMS)--were used. Use of MANOVA generated motivational profiles for students from both majors. The 320 student participants reported significant differences across various measures of learning motivation, with social work differing from engineering. Understanding why students choose certain majors has implications for instructors, programs, and institutions in regard to optimizing learning-teaching strategies, especially for those in increasingly interdisciplinary environments.

Keywords: Motivation, learning, engineering, social work, MANOVA, analysis, and research.

1. Introduction

A student's motivation to learn is a critical component to successful and sustained learning (Deci, 2009; Dweck, 2010; Elliot and Murayama, 2008). Likewise, understanding how students are motivated in choosing particular fields in higher education is useful for instructors when recruiting and designing teaching strategies. Recent research suggests that motivation is a key factor behind college students' career choices. Basham and Buchanan (2009) and Buchanan et al. (2007) compared social work students to business students. Both studies found that in general, social work students were more intrinsically motivated (i.e. motivation arising from within, like learning for its own sake) while business students were more externally motivated (i.e. focused on tangible rewards or pressures, like monetary gain and grades). Similarly, Hilmer and Hilmer (2012) studied 9,000 undergraduate students to understand how extrinsic motivation affects students' college choices: students wanting more financial attainment sought out majors like business and engineering.

In terms of motivation and degree persistence, Allen and Robbins (2008) studied 50,000 undergraduate college students to understand their sense of identity with their majors. Students reporting strong identification with their chosen major reported more motivation to adhere to that choice and graduate. Stronger academic performance was also associated with a motivation to persist in a chosen major. Persistence rates for different majors ranged anywhere from 43.1% to 77.6%, with engineering students having a rate of 76.5% (Allen and Robbins, 2008). Considering how interdisciplinary collaboration is typically a part of higher education and curriculum, as well as the workforce, it is essential to understand the underlying motivations that students have for learning. Understanding what motivates students across disciplines is crucial for the overall success of future students, instructors, and academic programs.

The current study seeks to expand the knowledge base on higher education pedagogy in terms of what motivates students to pursue and complete undergraduate programs; and, how student motivation compares across two majors, engineering and social work. Drawing on two well established theories, Self-Determination Theory and Achievement Goal Orientation Theory, this study examined undergraduate students' motivation in two distinct majors at a large university. It compared social work and engineering students across three scales measuring motivation to answer the study's primary research question: what motivates social work and engineering students during the course of their major program? The study's discovery of divergent motivational styles leads to further discussion of how universities and instructors may better prepare students of different fields for collaboration in interdisciplinary work environments.

2. Conceptual Framework

The traditional dichotomy of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation is not entirely realistic, especially as environmental elements change and influence students. Students can express both orientations at the same time, to varying degrees, depending on the circumstances and different environments they experience (Hidi and Harackiewicz, 2000; Lepper et al., 2005). It is for this reason that motivational scientists have broken down the dichotomous motivational influences into additional factors to determine other sources for human motivation. Several conceptual frameworks contribute to this process.

Self-Determination Theory (SDT) provides a framework for understanding different types of human motivational behaviors--i.e. intrinsic and extrinsic--with each falling on a continuum of inherent self-determination. SDT is a research-supported motivation theory that

encompasses three primary components for understanding motivation: autonomy, competence, and relatedness (Self-Determination Theory, 2014). Autonomy is having a sense of responsibility and ownership over one's learning (McCombs, 1991). Students who feel autonomous tend to act on their own, which often increases their intrinsic motivation (Deci and Ryan, 2008) and learning outcomes (Niemic and Ryan, 2009). Cameron et al. (2005) affirms the importance of individual autonomy, stating that students need to feel in control of their own actions to feel motivated. Competency occurs when one feels capable of accomplishing tasks that challenges one's own limits. Students, who report feeling competent at performing tasks, report increased interest in learning new skills and a sense of accomplishment (Niemic and Ryan, 2009). Relatedness is a student's positive interpersonal interactions with their peers and instructors. Students who feel positive relatedness tend to experience a sense of belonging and social support (Kaufman and Dodge, 2009). Beachboard et al. (2011) have pointed out that positive relatedness in learning environments can increase learning outcomes related to literacy, critical thinking, and job preparation.

Besides SDT, another useful predictor to motivation is situational motivation. Situational motivation adds the dimension of social environment as an influential factor, with Brunel (1999) affirming that environmental climate is often the biggest predictor of motivation. Situational motivation is defined as motivation one feels in the present moment, when involved in a specific, current activity (Vallerand, 1997). Motivation levels towards the specific, current activity is dependent on four key constructs. First, amotivation is similar to learned helplessness and reduces motivation. Second, external regulation involves motivational sources beyond one's control and influences one's behavior towards avoiding negative consequences. External regulation tends to reduce motivation. Thirdly, identified regulation is when a person accepts a reason for a behavior, and feels a sense of choice, which often increases motivation. Finally, intrinsic motivation involves actions that are internally and personally rewarding, which also increases motivation.

Achievement Goal Orientation Theory (AGOT) provides another framework for how students are oriented toward their motivation to learn (Darnon et al., 2007; Elliot and Murayama, 2008; Harackiewicz et al., 2008). AGOT identifies two primary motivational-orientations: performance orientation and learning orientation. Student can have either orientation in their academic attitude, application, or in both. People with performance orientations emphasize measuring their performance against others, often through rankings and grades. Performance-oriented students focus on how others perceive them, often with a tendency to expect immediate results that sometimes place them at risk for greater disappointment. In contrast, people with learning orientations would emphasize mastery and skill-acquisition over their subjects, over grades and comparison against others. Learning-oriented individuals perceive learning itself as the primary goal. Learning-oriented students often believe and behave as though learning is on a continuum of overall progress, without an end, whereas and performance-oriented person may focus more on the end-goal, i.e. grade. Learning-oriented individuals regard grades and results as of secondary importance.

AGOT includes two other variables: performance avoidance and work avoidance. Performance avoidance is when students avoid performance due psychological or social stress, such as fears of failure and lost confidence. Although students may wish to perform, they do not due to anxiety, which could cause them to miss constructive learning opportunities. Conversely, work avoidance occurs when a student reduces their work efforts (Harackiewicz, et al., 2008). Work avoidance is often inversely related to anxiety and fears of failure and is not conducive to students with learning orientations (Anderson and Dixon, 2009; Hirst et al., 2009; Houser and Frymier, 2009; Lee et al., 2010; Salinas and Garr, 2009).

These conceptual frameworks allow for eleven dependent variables (see Table 1) to be studied alongside with the study's independent variable, major.

Table 1. Definition of Variables

Self-Determination Theory	
Autonomy	A person's feeling of self-determination and personal decision making which likely increase motivation.
Competence	A person's feelings of being capable and able to accomplish a task in order to further a person's motivation.
Relatedness	A person's feeling of connection and relationships with others, which will likely increase motivation.
Achievement Goal Orientation	
Learning Orientation	The most optimal form of learning that has a lasting effect. Related to intrinsic motivation.
Performance Orientation	When people perform primarily for extrinsic reward, and usually to compete and perform better than others.
Performance Avoidance	Although these people want to work and perform, they avoid performance, usually out of fear of failure, which may be due to anxiety or looking bad in front of others.
Work Avoidance	When people simply do not want to work hard. The work avoidance is not connected to any type of anxiety related to the work.
Situational Motivation	
Amotivation	Similar to learned helplessness and usually occurs after a series of negative experiences. The person does not expect positive outcomes from their actions. A reduction in motivation occurs.

External Regulation	Being regulated by sources beyond one's own control, which influences a person's behavior, so the person avoids negative consequences. External Regulation tends to reduce motivation.
Identified Regulation	When someone identifies a personal reason and identified choice for their actions. Identified regulation increases motivation.
Intrinsic Motivation	When one's motivation is internally and personally rewarding, interesting, or feels good, and which increases motivation.

3. Research Design

Participants

Undergraduate students were recruited using convenience sampling at a large public southwestern university. The university's Internal Review Board for Human Subjects approved the survey. To incentivize survey participation, a random drafting of gift cards was offered. An email was broadcasted via a campus research recruitment source to locate participants, thus informing social work and engineering students about the opportunity to participate. A total of 320 undergraduate students were included in this sample: 198 engineering students (62%) and 122 social work students (38%).

Measurement Instruments

Undergraduate students were asked to respond to a 55-item survey over their particular major only. Online survey software helped with designing the questions. Students would first select their major, with the software embedding their major within each question (e.g. "In a social work course, I prefer...; In an engineering course, I prefer...").

The survey consisted of three scales: the Basic Psychological Needs Scale (BPNS; Deci and Ryan, 2000), the Achievement Goal Orientation Scale (AGOS; Harackiewicz et al., 2008) and the Situational Motivation Scale (SIMS; Guay et al., 2000). The survey included questions about each student's demographic information.

The Basic Psychological Needs Scale (BPNS) is a 21-item, self-report instrument that includes three subscales that measure autonomy, competence and relatedness (Deci and Ryan, 2000). Items are rated on a 7-point Likert scale from "1 = Not at All True" to "7 = Very True." These subscales have strong internal consistency (Autonomy = .84; Competence = .81; Relatedness = .92) and good test-retest reliability (Moutao et al., 2012).

The AGOS is an 18-item, self-report instrument that includes four subscales: learning orientation, performance orientation, performance avoidance, and work avoidance (Harackiewicz et al., 1997; Midgley et al., 1996; Pintrich and DeGroot, 1990; Pintrich and Garcia, 1991). All of these subscales have good reliability and validity, with items rated on a 7-point Likert scale from "1 = Not at All True of Me" to "7 = Very True of Me." All four scales also have a Cronbach's alphas range from .78 to .90 (Harackiewicz et al., 2008).

The Situational Motivational Scale (SIMS) is based on the premise that motivation could be measured while individuals are engaged in many different kinds of activities (Guay et al., 2000). The SIMS is a 16-item self-report instrument that studies amotivation (4 items), external regulation (4 items), identified regulation (4 items), and intrinsic motivation (4 items). Each item is rated on a 7-point Likert scale from "1 = Corresponds Not at All" to "7 = Corresponds Exactly." The four SIMS subscales demonstrate internal consistency (Cronbach's alphas for each scale follows: intrinsic motivation .95, identified regulation .80, external regulation .86, and amotivation .77). SIMS also exhibited adequate construct validity with correlation between dimensions (Guay et al., 2000; Standage et al., 2003).

4. Statistical Methodology

Using SPSS, a one-way multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA) generated motivational profiles for students from both majors. MANOVA was chosen to test the significant difference between the means among the two majors (engineering and social work) and the eleven dependent variables from the BPNS, AGOS, and SIMS measurement scales: autonomy, competence, relatedness, learning orientation, performance orientation, performance avoidance, work avoidance, amotivation, external regulation, identified regulation, and intrinsic motivation. An alpha level of .05 ($p < .05$) was used in order to test for significance.

5. Findings

Demographics

Among the 320 respondents, 198 were engineering majors and 122 were social work majors. As a total group, 38.1% were seniors, 28.1% were juniors, 17.5% were sophomores, and 16.3% were freshman. The average age of the participants was 21 years old. The group consisted of 52.5% women and 47.5% men. The majority of the participants were white (44.4%), followed by Asian-Americans (25.6%), Hispanics (23.1%), African-American (5.3%), and other races (1.6%). First generation college students comprised 36.3% of the sample. First generation college students were defined as students who stated that neither of their parents graduated from a four-year college. Underrepresented students (defined as African-American, Hispanic, Native-American, and/or first generation college students) comprised 41.9% of the total sample. Most students self-reported growing up as middle-class (37.8%), followed by upper middle-class (27.2%), lower middle-class (23.4%), lower-class (9.7%), and upper-class (1.9%).

Data Analysis

Table 2 shows the means and standard deviations for each of the two majors, next to the eleven dependent variables.

	Engineering <i>n</i> = 198	Social Work <i>n</i> = 122
	M(SD)	M(SD)
Autonomy	4.05 (0.81)	5.28 (0.83)
Competence	4.64 (0.97)	5.59 (0.86)
Relatedness	4.75 (1.13)	5.52 (0.98)
Learning Orientation	5.56 (0.91)	5.56 (0.56)
Performance Orientation	5.43 (1.20)	4.26 (1.52)
Performance Avoidance	4.99 (1.64)	5.27 (1.22)
Work Avoidance	2.82 (1.27)	2.30 (1.13)
Amotivation	1.97 (1.13)	1.61 (1.06)
External Regulation	2.75 (1.36)	2.19 (1.42)
Identified Regulation	5.77 (0.87)	5.75 (1.06)
Intrinsic Motivation	4.62 (1.26)	5.45 (1.11)
* <i>p</i> < .05		

A one-way multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA) tested the means between the majors and generated motivational profiles for students from each major. The multivariate result was significant for the independent variable, major. The results were: Pillai's Trace = .521, *F* = 30.508, *df* = (11, 308), partial η^2 = .521, and *p* = .000 (alpha value is less than .05) which indicates a significant difference between the two majors in at least one of the eleven motivational variables. Furthermore, the partial η^2 (.521) showed a strong effect size, when using the range for partial η^2 as: small=.01; medium=.09; large=.25 (Olsteen and Bright, 2010). Since the overall MANOVA was significant, separate ANOVAs comparing the mean differences were analyzed. The test comparing the differences between the means shows differences between the majors as described in Table 3 and Figures 1-3.

Table 3. Comparing the Mean Differences (Significance) between Engineering and Social Work Majors

Variable	Majors Mean (Sig.)
Autonomy	1.2276* (.000)
Competence	.9565* (.000)
Relatedness	.7668* (.000)
Learning Orientation	-.0077 (.933)
Performance Orientation	-1.1637* (.000)
Performance Avoidance	.2706 (.058)
Work Avoidance	-.5118* (.000)
Amotivation	-.3669* (.004)
External Regulation	-.5553* (.001)
Identified Regulation	-.0174 (.873)
Intrinsic Motivation	.8306* (.000)
* <i>p</i> < .05	

Figure 1. demonstrates the results from the Psychological Needs Scale (BPNS; Deci and Ryan, 2000), which measures autonomy, competence, and relatedness. For all three dependent variables, social work majors scored higher mean differences compared to engineering majors, with the difference being statistically significant across the board (autonomy = 5.28 to 4.05, competence = 5.59 to 4.64, relatedness = 5.52 to 4.75).

Figure 1. Comparing the Means for the Self-Determination Theory Variables

Figure 2 demonstrates the results from the Achievement Goal Orientation Scale (AGOS; Harackiewicz et al., 2008). The four variables measured were: learning orientation, performance orientation, performance avoidance, and work avoidance. Two of AGOS' variables showed no statistically significant difference. This included mean differences for the learning orientation (engineering majors = 5.56, social work majors = 5.56) and for performance avoidance (social work majors = 5.18, engineering majors = 4.91). Engineering majors scored higher (5.43) in performance orientation compared to social work majors (4.26). For work avoidance, engineering majors also scored higher (2.82) when compared to social work majors (2.30), with the difference being statistically significant at the $p < .05$ alpha level.

Figure 2. Comparing the Means for the Achievement Goal Orientation Variables

Figure 3 demonstrates the results from the Situational Motivation Scale (SIMS; Guay et al., 2000), which measures the variables: identified regulation, amotivation, external regulation, and intrinsic motivation. For identified regulation, the difference between the means for both majors was not statistically significant. Engineering students had a mean score of 5.77 and social work students had a mean score of 5.75. Engineering students had significantly higher amotivation and external regulation means scores (1.97 and 2.75, respectively) when compared to social work students' mean scores (1.61, 2.19), with the difference between means being significant at the $p < .05$ level. Social work students had significantly higher mean scores for intrinsic motivation (5.45) when compared to engineering majors (4.62), with significance being at the $p < .05$ level.

Figure 3. Comparing the Means for the Situational Motivation Scale Variables

The two majors' scores indicated certain patterns for the learning motivation variables. Both majors scored similar mean scores over learning orientation (5.56, 5.56), indicating that both have high motivation towards learning. The differences lie in whether their learning is a result of more extrinsic or intrinsic factors.

In general, the engineering students reported lower scores over feelings of autonomy, competence, relatedness, and intrinsic motivation towards their learning. Engineering majors scored higher on external regulation, a variable related to extrinsic motivation, because it includes motivational sources outside of personal control and behaviors to avoid negative consequences. These five variables indicate that engineering majors are less intrinsically motivated relative to social work majors. Compared to social work students, engineer majors scored lower for performance avoidance, which indicates lesser probability of fearing failure when performing.

Social work majors had a different profile from the engineering majors. Social Work majors indicated higher scores for autonomy, competence, relatedness, and intrinsic motivation; and lower scores for work avoidance, amotivation, performance orientation, and external regulation towards their learning. All eight variables' higher mean scores suggest that social work students tend to have greater intrinsic learning motivation levels. From these two discipline profiles, it appears that engineering students experience more extrinsic motivation while social work student's greater intrinsic motivation during the college course at the university.

6. Discussion and Implications

This study extends the dialogue about students for learning by looking across two disciplines simultaneously, particularly from the perspective of situational motivation. Social work students' report of higher motivation for pursuing their major is possibly due to having more intrinsic motivation when choosing the major. The study affirms the previously discussed studies that show social work majors' tendency to rate higher in intrinsic motivation when compared to other majors. Social work majors typically do not have excessive extrinsic rewards associated with their careers, like wealth and status, which are more commonly associated with engineering fields. The study's results are also consistent with other studies that describe engineering majors as having stronger extrinsic motivation (Basham & Buchanan, 2009; Buchanan et al., 2007; Hilmer and Hilmer, 2012).

Intrinsic and extrinsic motivation each have different effects on college students' long-term learning and performance. Intrinsically motivated individuals have several advantages over extrinsically motivated individuals. Intrinsic motivation encourages a greater degree of sustained learning (Cameron et al., 2005; Cho and Perry, 2012; Deci, 2009; Xiang et al., 2005). Such students tend to develop a higher regard for learning, without an over-reliance on immediate results and external rewards. In contrast, extrinsically motivated students are more dependent on rewards as a catalyst to their learning, which may not always be present. Generally, extrinsic rewards tend to decrease motivation over time (Deci et al., 1999). An overemphasis on extrinsic rewards can create other learning problems, such as students being tempted to cheat, arriving late more often, and reduced motivation and learning outcomes over the long-term (Anderman et al., 1998; Covington, 2000; Jabbar, 2011). Similarly, Vansteenkiste et al. (2005) found that extrinsic motivation reduced higher-level conceptual learning when compared to intrinsic motivation. In contrast, intrinsic motivation is positively correlated with more engagement in learning activities, better conceptual learning, and more persistence at learning activities (Vansteenkiste et al., 2006). Furthermore, Sebire et al. (2009) found that high intrinsic motivation among adults negatively predicted anxiety while positively predicting self-worth, increased exercise, well-being, and satisfaction.

Implications for Pedagogy

The study builds upon future research interested in student motivation and learning across disciplines, particularly those with different skill emphases and analytical frameworks. Motivational learning research can assist higher education instructors and departments seeking more sustainable forms of student learning and motivation. All motivation and learning studies are potentially useful for recruitment, raising learning outcomes, and for designing interdisciplinary collaboration.

One example of using data effectively is designing curriculums to promote improved feelings of autonomy towards the learning of one's major or subject. Intrinsic motivation is undermined when individuals are not given autonomy over certain aspects of learning. Individuals rewarded extrinsically can feel that they are being constrained, in a socially-controlled system (Vansteenkiste et al., 2005; Vansteenkiste et al., 2006). Hagger and Chatzisarantis (2011) similarly report that individuals who were given extrinsic rewards exhibited significantly lower intrinsic motivation. Similarly, other variables positively related to intrinsic motivation can be incorporated into the pedagogy.

Designing curriculum to improving intrinsic motivation may also help improve student mental health and reduce burn out. Mental health problems, retention, and dropout hinders a department's overall performance as well as affects the quality of life experience of the student (American College Health Association 2015b). According to Pisarik (2009) high intrinsic motivation and identified regulation correlated with lower burnout among undergraduate college students, while higher amotivation and external regulation positively correlated to burnout. Both students and universities would benefit from addressing such issues.

Lastly, this study adds further knowledge as to how universities and instructors may prepare students for collaboration within interdisciplinary work environments. Each discipline has unique strengths, which can be further studied, analyzed, borrowed, and synthesized with pre-existing teaching methods to increase students' motivation and learning outcomes. Educational institutions and instructors can become better interdisciplinary facilitators that skillfully integrate the best of each disciplinary method into their pedagogy. One concrete example, specifically related to engineering and social work principles, are U.S. universities that offer Humanitarian Engineering (Engineers Without Borders) that include social, policy, community building, and engineering needs for facilitating humanitarian efforts.

Implications for Interdisciplinary Practice among Students

Upon graduation, both engineering and social work students enter various work environments that expose them to professionals and clients from a wide variety of disciplines and motivational styles. Trends like globalization and the modern world's growing complexity increases the likelihood of such interdisciplinary encounters. Graduating students need to develop self-awareness, adaptability, and social intelligence of each other's motivations, to build work partnerships and to successfully handle complex community issues. This is true for social work students, who's training increasingly requires interdisciplinary collaboration (Gilbert, 2014). Success at interdisciplinary collaboration requires exposing students to complementary strengths and attitudes, such as the studied social work students' high intrinsic motivation and the engineering students' lower risk of performance avoidance.

Although collaboration between science-technology and social work students remain a recent phenomenon in our global collaborations, such collaborations can be advantageous. Gilbert (2014) demonstrates and discusses the soundness of an interdisciplinary education model regarding its ability to engage both engineering and social work students. One example includes, having interdisciplinary community projects that utilizes the technical and design knowledge of engineering majors and the community building and cultural knowledge of social work majors. The interdisciplinary model acknowledges how most real-life community problems go beyond the scope of any one discipline (Gilbert, 2014). Collaboration between social work and engineering disciplines can translate into more ambitious applications, like colleges and students that offer services to organizations centered around international development projects. By bringing together social workers and engineers to create meaningful change in communities, it is vital to understand how their unique motivational styles can be better drawn towards successful work outcomes. Ultimately, this can lead to community-generated solutions that yields long-term benefits.

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